

RESEARCHING INTUITIVE INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

Intuitive interaction is based on past experience and is fast and often non conscious. We have conducted ten studies into this issue over the past ten years, involving more than 400 participants. Data collection methods have included questionnaires, interviews, observations, concurrent and retrospective protocols, and cognitive measures. Coding schemes have been developed to suit each study and involve robust, literature based heuristics. Some other researchers have investigated this issue and their methods are also examined. The paper traces the development of the methods and compares the various approaches used over the years.

Keywords: Intuitive interaction, research methodology, observational analysis

INTRODUCTION

Our intuitive interaction research was begun in 2000 with the aim of establishing whether users can transfer knowledge from other products in order to use the various features of a new one. Intuition was defined as a type of cognitive processing that is fast, often non-conscious and utilises stored experiential knowledge. Intuitive interaction therefore involves the use of knowledge gained from other products and/or experiences (Blackler, 2008b). This paper will focus on the methods used by us and others to investigate this complex issue over the past decade. The paper has three main sections. Stage 1 details the initial empirical work we did - the first to investigate intuitive interaction. The second compares the methodologies used by other researchers in the field. The third details our more recent and expanding research, particularly focussing on intuitive interaction for older people.

STAGE 1: UNDERSTANDING THE NATURE OF INTUITIVE INTERACTION

In Stage 1, three experiments were conducted, with a total of 110 participants. We used real, contemporary products as mediators to reveal participant knowledge. This approach was intended to ensure that the experiments were ecologically valid. It was also important to get a variety and mix of common (familiar) and uncommon (unfamiliar) features in order to be able to design an experiment that allowed comparison of how easily people can use familiar and unfamiliar features. Also, new product types that would require transfer of existing knowledge from elsewhere were favoured, which allowed the experiment to test whether or not familiar features from other product types could be transferred. An early digital camera was used for Experiment 1 and a re-configurable, touchscreen universal remote control was used for Experiments 2 and 3 (Blackler, 2008b).

TECHNOLOGY FAMILIARITY

Technology familiarity (TF) was used in all three experiments to gauge past experience with relevant interface features. It was measured through a questionnaire, in which participants provided details of their experience with products with similar features to those they would encounter during the experiment. A separate questionnaire was therefore devised for each new product used in the experiments. More frequent and more extensive use of the products in the questionnaire produces a higher TF score (Blackler & Hurtienne, 2007; Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2010b). Hurtienne, Horn, & Langdon (2010) discuss facets of prior experience and identify the facets of exposure,

competence and subjective feeling. Exposure is split into three sub-components - duration, intensity and diversity of use. Duration describes how many months/years a product has been used. Intensity describes how often it is used, and diversity of use describes the number of functions/features used, or problems solved with the product. In addition, Hurtienne et. al. (2010) suggest that three levels of specificity apply to exposure and competence. These are (1) the product in focus, (2) different products of the same type, and (3) a broad range of products of different types. Our TF questionnaires were designed to measure exposure (intensity and diversity) at all three levels of specificity, as interface features are often transferred between products and product types. For example, the remote control we used for Experiments 2 and 3 had tab-based navigation similar to software alongside standard audiovisual symbols found on all kinds of remote controls and audiovisual devices.

EXPERIMENT DESIGNS

The procedure of each experiment was almost identical. Participants were video-recorded performing set tasks with the products whilst performing concurrent (think aloud) protocol. Then they were interviewed about their familiarity with each interface feature they used. The experiment designs for these three experiments differed somewhat. Experiment 1 had participants grouped by self-reported expertise with digital cameras, and balanced for gender and education. Experiment 1 showed that TF based on products that had similar features to the test product was more relevant than self-reported expertise with the same product type. Therefore, Experiment 2 saw participants grouped by TF and balanced for gender, age and education. Experiment 2 results suggested that age may be a factor that was worth investigating. Experiment 3 therefore had participants grouped by both age and interface group (4 different interfaces to investigate importance of appearance and location of features). They were matched for TF, level of education and gender.

CODING DATA

The coding scheme employed for this research assumed that various levels of cognitive processing

occur during one task (Berry & Broadbent, 1988), and was designed to distinguish intuitive processing from other processes (such as automatic and conscious processes). Every feature use for all participants was coded with Noldus Observer. These results were then exported to an Excel spreadsheet for further manipulation (e.g. weeding out intuitive uses from other uses and calculating percentages) and then into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for full statistical analysis.

At this stage, every feature use was coded because it was the use of individual product features that was important, rather than use of the product as a whole. This is because it is not the product, but its features, with which users have relevant past experience. The definition of a feature, as the term is used here, is a feature of a product that is discrete from others, has its own function, location and appearance and can be designed separately from other features. A shutter button on a camera, a print icon on software or an earpiece on a stereo are all examples of features.

The dependant variables common to all the experiments in Stage 1 were time on tasks, number or percentage of intuitive uses and intuitive first uses and subjective measures of familiarity of product features. Time on task is relevant as intuitive processing is assumed to be faster than more conscious types of processing (Agor, 1986; Bastick, 2003; Salk, 1983), so participants interacting intuitively with the product should be able to complete tasks more quickly. However, it cannot be assumed that completing the task quickly is always the same as completing it intuitively; there also needs to be a measure of intuition or intuitive uses. The way in which intuitive uses were extracted from the data and coded is discussed in detail below. Table 1 shows the coding scheme used for these three experiments.

Correctness

A “correct” use was taken to be one that was correct for the feature and also correct for the task or subtask at the moment of use. A “correct-but-inappropriate” use was one that was correct for the feature but not for the task or subtask. “Incorrect” uses were wrong for both the feature and the task or subtask and “attempts” were uses that did not

register with the product, for example due to failure to activate a button on the touch screen.

Behaviours	Modifiers	Categories within modifier
Feature used	Correct-ness of use	Correct
18 for camera		Correct for feature but inappropriate for task
19 for remote control	Type of use	Incorrect
		Attempted
		Intuitive use
		Quick use
		Use by trial and error
	Logical reasoning use	
	Getting help use	
	Mistaken use	

Table 1. Coding Scheme used for Stage 1

Type of use

The definition of intuitive use formulated for the purposes of this research states that intuitive use involves utilising knowledge gained through other experience(s), is fast and can be non-conscious. The coding heuristics used to determine which uses were intuitive were based on this definition and on the literature on intuition. The main indicators of intuitive uses that were employed to make the decisions about types of use during the coding process are explained below.

Evidence of conscious reasoning

Since intuitive processing does not involve conscious reasoning or analysis (Agor, 1986; Bastick, 2003; Fischbein, 1987; Hammond, 1993; Noddings & Shore, 1984), the less reasoning was evident for each use, the more likely it was that intuitive processing was happening. Commonly, participants processing intuitively would not verbalise the details of their reasoning. They may briefly verbalise a whole sub-task rather than all the steps involved; or they would start to press a button and then stop to explain what they were about to do; or perform the function and then explain it afterwards. Their verbalisation was not in time with their actions if they were processing unconsciously while trying to verbalise consciously.

Expectation

Intuition is based on prior experience and therefore linked to expectations (Dreyfus, Dreyfus, & Athanasiou, 1986; Klein, 1998). If a participant clearly had an established expectation that a feature

would perform a certain function when s/he activated it, s/he could be using intuition.

Subjective certainty of correctness

Researchers have suggested that intuition is accompanied by confidence in a decision or certainty of correctness (Bastick, 2003; Hammond, 1993), and degree of confidence has been used in some experimental situations as an index of intuition (Eysenck, 1995; Westcott, 1961). Those uses coded as intuitive were those that participants seemed certain about, not when they were just trying a feature out.

Latency

When users were able to locate and use a feature reasonably quickly, it could be coded as intuitive. Intuition is generally fast (Agor, 1986; Bastick, 2003; Hammond, 1993; Salk, 1983), and time to make a move can be used to measure thinking time (Cockayne, Wright, & Fields, 1999). If a participant had already spent some time exploring other features before hitting upon the correct one, that use was unlikely to be intuitive. Those uses coded as intuitive involved the participants using the right feature with no more than five seconds hesitation, commonly closer to one or two seconds.

Relevant past experience

Participants would sometimes mention during concurrent protocol that a feature was like one they had used before, or that they had seen a feature before, showing evidence of their existing knowledge.

“Intuitive use” codes were applied cautiously, only when the use showed two or more of these characteristics and the researcher was certain about the type of use. Any uses about which there was doubt were coded as “quick use” rather than “intuitive”.

OUTCOMES FROM STAGE 1

All three experiments conducted during these years showed that intuitive interaction is based on past experience with similar products and product features. Familiar features were used more intuitively, and people with higher TF completed tasks more quickly, with more intuitive uses and less errors. Appearance of features seems to be more important than location for intuitive interaction. Results also suggested that older people, even those

with higher TF, completed tasks more slowly and less intuitively than younger people. Based on these results, a set of principles for intuitive interaction and a draft tool for applying it to the design process were developed (Blackler, 2008b). Through these experiments, we developed a robust coding scheme supported by literature-based heuristics, which we have built on since. The TF questionnaire proved reliable, and has been used subsequently by us as well as adapted by others (O'Brien, 2010).

This intensive feature based methodology was also adapted to a commercial project. We were asked to compare two models of the same product type for intuitiveness. Sixteen participants were divided into two groups of eight, with one group assigned to use each model. Each group was composed of a balanced selection of participants based on their age, educational background, TF score and gender. All participants were video-recorded performing the same four tasks with their product. These tasks were designed with two objectives in mind:

- To be realistic tasks that users would actually undertake.
- To force the participants to use as many features of the interfaces as possible.

Following the tasks, participants were asked to rate their familiarity with the features of the product interface, and how difficult they found each of the tasks.

Coding all sixteen experiments, with four tasks in each, was obviously a time consuming process when every feature use had to be coded, which was a disadvantage of this methodology for the purposes of commercial research. However, this approach did allow us to study the features of the two models very closely and to provide detailed feedback to the client on exactly how the interfaces compared and how each feature could be improved.

OTHER RESEARCHERS' APPROACHES

There are other researchers doing work on prior experience, especially for older people. They have used methods very similar to ours - observing participants performing tasks with products such as microwaves, cameras and cars (Langdon, Lewis, & Clarkson, 2007; Lewis, Langdon, & Clarkson, 2008). One other researcher has studied the issue of intuitive interaction in depth. Another has studied

prior experience and older people but drawn heavily on our work on intuitive interaction. Their work will be discussed in detail here.

Image Schemas

Hurtienne (2009) conducted a range of studies examining the role of image schemas in intuitive use. Image schemas are abstract representations of recurring dynamic patterns of bodily interactions that structure the way we understand the world (Johnson, 1987), and thus are important building blocks for thinking. They are based on each individual's experience of interaction with the physical world, but tend to be largely universal as the physical world operates in the same way for everyone. Because they are based on past experience, and because they are so well known and so universal that they become unconscious, they can be defined as intuitive. Therefore, Hurtienne argues, incorporating image schemas into interfaces can allow intuitive interaction.

One of the most prominent image schemas is the up-down schema, with up often being associated with more, and down with less. An up-down schema (along with a left-right schema), for example, may be represented by a mini joystick on a mobile phone. When the joystick is moved, the cursor or highlighted menu selection moves with it. The up-down schema can be used equally well for representing abstract concepts such as speaker volume or attractiveness ratings.

Hurtienne used custom software to test the metaphorical extensions of image schemas applied to interface design. The software automatically measured the dependant variables - accurate responses to dialogue box instructions and response times. For Studies 1 and 2 (up-down image schema), the software would present a word or statement, priming the participant in relation to an image schema, and a dialogue box would then appear, which the participant would interact with. The interaction would either be compliant or non-compliant with the image schema. Studies 3 and 4 (near-fear image schema) used an automated process to test similarities or differences between values presented either numerically or visually. The values were displayed in various positions on a 3x3 grid. All these studies supported the notion that using

metaphorical extensions of image schemas in the software contributed to accurate and intuitive use. Hurtienne's final three studies use a more qualitative approach. Study 5 used a focus group style workshop to generate a list of real world examples of image schemas. The examples from this list were refined and then presented to four participants who specified which image schema applied to the example. The dependant variable was the consistency with which the image schemas were applied. Study 6 saw two participants specify image schemas for commercially available accounting software. Again, the dependant variable was consistency of the application of schemas. The final study involved a redesign of the software interface from Study 6, using image schemas. Users of the original software evaluated the new interface designs. The results showed that both the redesigned graphical user interface and a hybrid graphical/tangible interface were rated higher than the existing system.

Through his research, Hurtienne (2009) has demonstrated that metaphorical extensions of image schemas can be used in interface design, and they do result in better performance. The effective use of image schemas and their metaphorical extensions is likely to facilitate intuitive use, as image schemas are based on prior knowledge that almost every person possesses. Thus, performance using interfaces based upon image schemas should remain consistent across heterogeneous user groups, making them more ubiquitously applicable than familiar features, which may not be familiar to everyone and generally rely on experience with other products.

Prior Experience and Age

O'Brien (2010) has conducted a study into prior experience and its effect on technology use for older people, drawing heavily on our previous work (e.g. Blackler, 2008). She used an adapted version of our TF questionnaire to determine participant groups. First she conducted a longitudinal (10 day) diary study combined with interviews to investigate real life use of a variety of products by younger adults, high TF older adults and low TF older adults. She found that older adults used different categories of technologies - including more healthcare and kitchen products - than younger adults. High TF older adults

used more technologies than low TF older adults. She also showed that prior experience was the most common reason for successful technology use, but was not always sufficient on its own. Information presented by the products themselves was also needed to address problems encountered in real life tasks.

O'Brien then followed with an observation study very similar to our Stage 1 experiments. She video-recorded younger adults, high TF older adults and low TF older adults completing tasks with three different contemporary products (video camera, e-reader and digital radio alarm clock). This was followed by an interview about participants' familiarity with the features of the products and similar features they may have encountered elsewhere.

She performed two levels of coding - one which coded every feature use as we did in Stage 1, and one that looked at performance of overall tasks. Her dependant variables were correctness of feature uses (valid or invalid), references to information outside of their own experience (eg help from product labels, or from researcher), and task performance (optimal, successful or partial). Again she found that prior experience is important for technology use, but it did not explain all the differences between age groups. High TF older adults did not perform as well as younger adults.

These methods have some differences from ours, with use of diary studies, focus groups and workshops. But Hurtienne and O'Brien also used some similar methods, such as observation of participants performing set tasks with products and software, adaptation of our TF questionnaire, and post task interviews. With these diverse methods, Hurtienne and O'Brien have both consistently showed that fast, effective, intuitive interaction is based on past experience.

STAGE 2: INTUITIVE INTERACTION FOR OLDER PEOPLE

Following on from the foundational work described above, our program of research began to focus on intuitive interaction for older people. Five experiments have now been conducted investigating this issue. Aspects of intuitive interaction and ageing investigated through these studies include:

- Cognitive decline and ageing
- Familiarity in different age groups
- Redundancy in interface design
- Anxiety, self efficacy and interface complexity

All of these experiments have shown that prior experience contributes to faster, more intuitive and more correct use of the products and interfaces. This major finding from our foundational research has been repeated again and again in our further work and the work of others reported above. This discussion will confine itself to the methods used in the new experiments, and the other findings they have produced.

COGNITIVE DECLINE AND AGEING

A new experiment was designed to investigate the differences in task performance times, intuitive uses, and correct uses between three different age groups and two different microwave interfaces. This was a matched subjects 2x3 experiment design. Independent variables were age group and microwave interface and dependant variables were time, percentage of correct uses, and percentage of intuitive correct uses. Participants were video-recorded performing three tasks on touchscreen prototypes while delivering concurrent protocol. Based on Baddeley's model of working memory (Baddeley, 2000), we devised a battery of computer-based tests to measure a range of Working Memory functions. They were all administered on the touchscreen. Phonological Loop capacity was measured via a digit span task using a staircase procedure. Visuo-spatial Sketchpad capacity was measured using a Corsi Block task controlled by a staircase procedure. Sustained attention was assessed using a vigilance task where participants viewed pairs of shapes displayed for one second each and had to respond by touching a button on the touchscreen whenever the pair were identical. The capacity of the Central Executive to manipulate phonological and spatial information was measured using two transform tasks. In the phonological transform task, participants had to retain a four digit string in memory while moving each digit forward by four places. In the visual transform task, participants were required to retain in memory a set of four locations whilst moving each location forward by a four places. The software recorded reaction time

and accuracy. Raw values, rather than age adjusted values, were used.

This experiment revealed older people were slower and had less intuitive and less correct uses than younger ones. A regression analysis then showed that both TF and Central Executive function, which is related to aging, have more impact on time, correct uses and intuitive uses than chronological age (Blackler, Mahar, & Popovic, 2010a). A further experiment utilising a similar battery of tests revealed similar findings, again the suggesting that central executive function (specifically attention) had more effect on correct, speedy and intuitive use than age per se (Reddy, Blackler, Mahar, & Popovic, 2010). These results may help to explain why O'Brien's (2010) high TF older adults did not perform as well as the younger adults in her observations.

LEVELS OF FAMILIARITY IN DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS

The two experiments described in this section examined familiarity and prior knowledge, and methods to elicit relevant prior knowledge from participants that would be suitable for use in the design industry context. These experiments were designed to be mobile, which created a more representative sample of the older age groups. Physical products were used in both experiments. The data were coded using Atlas.ti and Noldus Observer, and then analysed using SPSS. Each step performed by participants during the task observation was coded. "Steps" were any action the participant made that involved the product they interacted with, such as picking up a remote, or entering time on a microwave. Data input, such as entering a phone number, or time in a microwave, was coded as a single step, rather than multiple steps.

Coding heuristics

The coding schemes used in these two experiments had the same foundation - familiarity. All raw data was coded for accuracy and also with three levels of familiarity: (1) very familiar, (2) moderately familiar and (3) not familiar. Some of our earlier heuristics for coding intuitive interaction have been integrated into this coding scheme, which is discussed below.

Forward Planning and Anticipation

Participants highly familiar with a string of steps would often integrate the following step into the one that they were currently executing. Anticipation has increasingly been acknowledged as an important element of high performance across multiple disciplines (Williams & Ward, 2007). This would often manifest in preparatory actions that would make the following step easier and faster, for example positioning a finger over a button that executes the next task, while waiting for a system to perform a particular action.

Relative Speed

We previously used latency (speed of each feature use) as one indicator of intuitive use. Relativity has been added to this due to the variation in cognitive and physical abilities of younger and older individuals (Hawthorn, 2000; Vercruyssen, 1997; Zajicek, 2004). A step that is slower than other steps by the same participant may indicate a lower level of familiarity, and a faster action may indicate a higher level of familiarity.

Verbalisation

Both highly detailed verbalisation and a lack of verbalisation can be viewed as a sign of high levels of familiarity. Chi (2006b) suggests that experts often verbalise more about more subtle and complicated elements. During task execution or task recall, very familiar participants would occasionally verbalise multiple options for a particular task. Verbalisation that reflects a high level of comprehension of the task, product, or domain is a sign of high familiarity. However, very low to no verbalisation can also suggest very high familiarity. Chi (2006a) reports that experts sometimes fail to recall more superficial features, and will often miss smaller details. We also previously found that participants often have low verbalisation levels when processing intuitively. Often participants would perform tasks with high familiarity and not verbalise at all, even though they had been instructed to.

Low verbalisation can also suggest low levels of familiarity. It was observed that verbalisation was lowest when participants were struggling to identify the next step to take. In our previous work, we would prompt participants to verbalise in this kind of situation. Often, in this study, once the problem had been solved, participants would start to verbalise

again as if nothing had happened. When a participant had low or no verbalisation, other heuristics were used to identify if this was a sign of low or high familiarity.

Situational Awareness and Perception

Unfamiliar participants would often overlook crucial functions, and misunderstand icons or other embedded knowledge. Alternatively, familiar participants would know exactly what a button did without more than a glance, could tell if an SD-Card was inserted properly by the feel of the click in the camera, or would know intuitively where a control would be.

Experiments

Both experiment used 32 participants in four age groups. Field Experiment 1 was conducted in the participant's home with a product that s/he considered him/herself to be familiar with. Many products were chosen by the participants, from mobile phones, to kitchen and laundry equipment, to TVs and stereos. A questionnaire was used to attempt to identify current product usage. A semi-structured interview was conducted next, going into more depth about the product the participant chose as familiar. The participant was then required to describe how s/he performed a common task with the product (we called this "task recall"). S/he then performed that task with the product, while delivering concurrent protocol. A retrospective protocol was completed after the observation. The dependant variables were familiarity and accuracy (identified through the coding scheme). Time to complete tasks was not relevant as all participants were completing different tasks on their chosen products.

Findings from this experiment suggested that there was a significant difference in familiarity between the youngest age group (17-39) and the two oldest age groups (60-74 and 75+). Some potential methods for eliciting familiarity were also identified (Lawry, Popovic, & Blackler, 2009; Lawry, Popovic, & Blackler, 2010).

Experiment 2 built on Field Experiment 1. This study focused on the use of products that participants were not familiar with. Four products were selected for all participants to use - two alarm clocks and two cameras. Each participant read a task sheet, and was

then shown the product briefly. The participant then explained how s/he thought s/he would perform the specified task (“primed task recall”). The participant then performed the task while delivering concurrent protocol. Then a short interview was conducted, asking about which aspects of the task the participants found difficult and why. This process was repeated for each product (order of presentation of the four products was counterbalanced). The dependant variables were familiarity and accuracy, identified through the coding scheme.

Findings from Experiment 2 suggested that, with products that participants had never used before, there was a significant difference in familiarity between the youngest age groups and all three of the older ones.

Middle aged people (40-59) were significantly different to younger ones in Experiment 2 but not in Field Experiment 1. This implies that middle aged people are able to learn about and become familiar with products they own but, just like older people, show significantly less familiarity with products that are new to them than younger people (Lawry, Popovic, & Blackler, 2011).

REDUNDANCY IN INTERFACE DESIGN

This experiment was designed to investigate whether new technologies could be made more intuitive for older people by employing redundancy in interface design. The design of the experiment was based on our previous studies detailed in Stage 1, with participants completing two set tasks with one of three interfaces. Also, the cognitive test battery was re-employed, and participants completed these tests after the rest of the experiment was done. It used a matched subjects design, with groups balanced for level of education, gender and Technology Familiarity.

The Independent Variables for this experiment were interface design (Words only, Symbols only and Redundant [both words and symbols]), and age group (5 groups). The data collection methods included observation, interviews, and concurrent verbal protocol, and an audio-visual recording of each experiment was made. This data was coded in Noldus Observer and analysed in SPSS. A software prototype of a body-fat analyser, a non-invasive self-care

health product, was used on a touchscreen. 44 participants took part, ranging in age from 18-83. The Dependant Variables were the time taken to accomplish the two set tasks, intuitive events observed and help required. For this experiment, we coded events rather than features. A task comprises of a set number of events, and each event needs one or more actions to complete. For example, inputting participant’s age is an event, and this event includes the actions pressing up or down arrow and pressing the OK button. There were 8 “events” embedded in the set tasks. The coding heuristics were based on those used previously:

- Intuitive use: Fast decision with no evident reasoning. Often there is lack of verbalisation and at times verbalisation follows an action.
- Correct (non intuitive) use: participant completing an event successfully with use of reasoning. Indicated by hesitation in action, time delay between the exposure to the activity and action, and verbalisation preceding the action.
- Incorrect use: Participant is unable to complete an event. Indicated by using the wrong function or overlooking the right one.
- Help (clue): Participants were provided with a clue after at least 30 seconds from the point of error.
- Help (explicit): Participants were provided with help to complete the activity after at least two minutes from the initial help clue.

Surprisingly, findings showed that that older people (65+ years) completed the tasks on the Words only interface faster, more intuitively and with less help than on the Redundant interface. The rest of the participants completed the tasks significantly faster and more intuitively on the redundant interface (Reddy et al., 2010; Reddy, Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2009). This suggests that the extra information presented in a redundant interface may cause excess cognitive load and so impede use of the interface by older people (Reddy, Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2011).

ANXIETY, INTERFACE COMPLEXITY AND INTUITIVE USE

This experiment was designed to investigate the relationships between age, anxiety and intuitive use of complex technological devices. There is some research which indicates that older people can experience more anxiety when it comes to interacting with new technologies (Eisma et al., 2003). It was also established by Bastick (2003) that stress, anxiety and oppressive environments are not conducive to intuitive thinking. However, what is not well understood is the impact of these conditions on intuitive use of a product. Our earlier studies on intuitive interaction found no significant differences in intuitive use between those who are anxious and those who are not. However, these experiments were not specifically designed to look at the impact of anxiety on intuitive interaction. We used only a one question self-report measure of anxiety, and the experiment protocol was carefully designed to remove uncertainty and anxiety from participants. The design of this experiment addressed these shortcomings.

This experiment was again based on those conducted previously and used a mixed between- and within-participants design. Independent variables were age group (5 groups), complexity of interface (complex/nested or simple/flat) and induced anxiety (positive or negative performance feedback). The dependent variables were time on task, errors and percentage of intuitive interactions. Overall 50 participants (10 each in five age groups) participated in this experiment. Participants were balanced for TF, perceived self-efficacy and education level. Cognitive measures were also re-employed. As in our earlier work, data collection methods were observation of interaction, interviews and rating scales.

Participants were asked to complete two real-life style tasks with a virtual pet on a touch sensitive tablet (iPad). In between tasks, participants completed a short form State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) (Spielberger, Gorsuch, Lushene, & Press, 1968) and answered various questions about the difficulty of the task. The tasks were counterbalanced to avoid training and sequencing effects. Two cameras were used to record the experiment for later analysis using Noldus Observer software. The coding scheme

operates in a similar way to that in the redundancy study. Analysis of this experiment is currently underway.

DISCUSSION

The last decade of research has produced a firm understanding of intuitive interaction and begun to unravel the reasons behind differences in interface use between older and younger people. It is encouraging to note that several different researchers on three different continents using a variety of products and experiment designs have all found that prior experience is the leading contributor to intuitive use (Blackler, 2008b; Hurtienne, 2009; O'Brien, 2010). However, lower familiarity affects people from middle age onwards (Lawry et al., 2011), while the performance of older people is affected by decline in central executive function as well as lower familiarity (Blackler et al., 2010a; Reddy et al., 2010). The development of robust and detailed methods has allowed these discoveries to occur. Teasing out these complex issues would not have been possible without such formalised methods.

METHODS AND APPROACHES

All intuitive interaction research has taken a mainly quantitative approach even though much of the data collected has been qualitative. From our point of view, the main reason for this is that the most successful way to investigate such rich and complex data was believed to be through statistical analysis. Also, due to the novel nature of this research, we felt that quantitative measures would be required to support the claims made. In addition, all of our work has required use of percentages rather than counts of behaviours/uses/errors/steps. This allows for proper comparisons between participants - such as between age groups, interface groups, etc. If this was not done an interface that required more "steps" or "uses" would not be able to be compared against one that required less, for example. The methods used by us and others to investigate intuitive interaction, and the related area of prior experience, have been various, but the underpinning approach has been video-recorded observation of people performing tasks with real or prototyped interfaces. Several other methods (e.g. surveys,

diaries, questionnaires, interviews, verbal protocols and cognitive tests) have been successfully used to supplement it, and automated software has sometimes been utilised to collect some of the performance data (e.g. Hurtienne, 2009). However, it is unlikely that any other method could completely replace this approach as this is the only way researchers can see and understand what real people actually do with products and interfaces.

Coding schemes based on the literature have been used to analyse this data - focussing on correctness, speed and intuitiveness or familiarity of the interaction. The early approach of coding every feature use may not be necessary now that an understanding of intuitive use has been well established. It is likely that our more recent approach of coding "events" or "steps" will be the way forward in most cases. We have used this approach successfully, as did O'Brien for part of her coding. The advantage of this is that it saves time and allows the research to focus on aspects other than feature uses (e.g. participants' understanding of task procedures).

USE OF PROTOTYPES

Many of the experiments described here have used real products, including cars, cameras, microwaves, alarm clocks, e-readers, video cameras, and remote controls (plus all the various products chosen by participants in the first familiarity experiment). However, some prototyped interfaces have also been used by us and others (e.g. Hurtienne, 2009). In many experimental situations this is necessary as it allows researchers to test differences between interface designs, but it is not without its problems. Touchscreen prototypes have been employed in several of our experiments. These were:

- two different microwave interfaces - one of them designed to be more intuitive than the other.
- three different interfaces for a body fat monitor - Words, Symbols and Redundant.
- two different software interfaces mocking up a virtual pet task - nested and flat.

Issues encountered include difficulties in creating suitable software prototypes, representing and conveying a three dimensional object in two dimensions, prototype and interface sizing and

scaling, and representations of LCD displays on a touch screen (Blackler, 2008a). Each time, the prototype development has been a success after a lot of effort. Strategies to get around the kinds of issues encountered can work successfully (e.g. see Blackler, 2008a), but need to be well thought out and well tested. Hawthorn (2007) also notes that older people find it difficult to work with low-fidelity prototypes and suggests making testing environments as realistic as possible. Hence, we have used only high fidelity prototypes.

FIELDWORK

The majority of our experiments have been conducted in the People and Systems Laboratory (PAS Lab) at Queensland University of Technology. However, the first familiarity experiment was done completely in the field in order to allow more realistic assessment of the things that were familiar around participants' homes. The second familiarity experiment was also made to be mobile to allow for easier participant recruitment, particularly for older people, who tend to be reluctant to travel to our laboratory in the CBD. In fieldwork, extraneous variables need to be controlled as far as possible, so that the differences in the environment do not confound the experiment. It is also important for the researcher to treat each participant consistently despite the differing environments so that results will be comparable. Having learnt these valuable lessons, we expect to be doing more fieldwork, including investigating intuitive interaction and navigation within large scale environments.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

After a decade of research, much has been done but much remains to be done. We are finalising the current work on intuitive interaction for older people, and already more issues to be investigated have come out of that. For example, we have developed and started to run an experiment to investigate the psychological underpinnings of intuitive interaction and whether they differ between age groups. We are also aiming to establish methods for designers to apply intuitive use to new interfaces, for older and younger people. Our early draft tool for this purpose has some advantages and works to some extent, but needs consolidating

(Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2006). We are in the process of developing the Familiarity Identification Tool (FIT) to assist design professionals to identify familiarity that is suitable for application to a product/system they design. However, the robust methods we have developed have stood the test of time. They have been adapted by us and by others, have been applied to differing participant groups across the world and across age ranges, have employed a variety of real and prototyped interfaces, and have produced consistent and reliable results on which we can continue to build.

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